

PHENOMENON-BASED TEACHING AND LEARNING THROUGH THE PEDAGOGICAL, PRACTICAL OPTIC OF PHENOMENOLOGY

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Abstract. *PBL is an innovative pedagogical approach that emphasizes experiential learning through real-world phenomena. It encourages students to actively engage in the learning process by immersing themselves in authentic, contextualized scenarios. By integrating technology, PBL offers unique opportunities to enhance learning as well teaching by providing dynamic auditory experiences and tailored feedback.*

Keywords: *phenomena, phenomenology, constructivism, multidisciplinary learning modules, curriculum reform, Finland.*

Introduction:

In today's fast-paced and interconnected world, effective communication skills have become more important than High school ever. Students need to develop strong speaking abilities to succeed in various academic, personal, and professional settings. Phenomenon-based learning (PBL) technology offers a promising approach to enhancing students' speaking skills by providing them with engaging and interactive learning experiences. This article explores the potential benefits of incorporating PBL technology into high school classrooms and highlights its role in fostering students' speaking proficiency.

1. Understanding Phenomenon-Based Learning Technology and toward a phenomenon-based approach in Finnish education.

Phenomenon-based learning technology is an innovative educational approach that focuses on real-world phenomena and encourages students to actively explore, investigate, and collaborate to understand complex concepts. By integrating technology into this framework, educators can create immersive learning environments that enhance students' speaking skills.

In the last 16 years, Finland's education system has been regarded as one of the best in the world, receiving major media publicity, international recognition and respect. Each year educators, researchers, experts and various interest groups visit Finland in search of “the holy grail” of education, expecting to gain new ideas and insights they could apply back home. The OECD's Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), an internationally benchmarked study that assesses the competences of 15-year-olds in reading, math and science every three years, has steadily ranked Finland's among the world's top-performing education systems since the study's launch in 2000.

Although Finnish students' test scores declined in the latest PISA results, Finland remains high in the league tables and receives similar results in IEA's TIMSS and PIRLS1 -(IEA, 2012). The “Finnish miracle,” as the media have called it, is well documented by Pasi Sahlberg in his work “Finnish Lessons.” Sahlberg (2011, pp. 128-131) identified five reasons to explain the success behind the good educational performance of the Finnish comprehensive education system: (a) *Peruskoulou* – the nine-year compulsory school – offers equal educational opportunities for all; (b) teaching is an inspiring profession that attracts many young Finns; In light of this plethora of reforms, this topic will focus on the analysis of the phenomenon-based approach in teaching

and learning, a pedagogical initiative that has received wide media coverage and publicity, because of the news that Finland has moved away from traditional subject teaching and toward multidisciplinary learning modules. The initial exaggerated reaction of Finland’s abolishing subject teaching proved misleading, as it soon became clear that subjects remain in place, while Finnish education will officially introduce study periods in which students will be working with several teachers across subjects on phenomenon-based project.

An overview of phenomenon-based teaching and learning.

In “How to create the school of the future: revolutionary thinking and design from Finland,” Mattila and Silander (2015) develop their thinking on phenomenon-based teaching and learning within the context of digital pedagogy. Silander (2015a, p. 16) argues that holistic real-world phenomena help initiate learning, provided they “are studied as complete entities, in their real context, and the information and skills related to them are studied by crossing the boundaries between subjects.” Examples of phenomena can include such topics as climate change, the European Union, media and technology, water or energy. A phenomenon is thus seen as:

- » An authentic object of observation.
- » A systemic framework for the things to be learned (systemic model).
- » A metaphorical framework for the things to be learned (analogous model).
- » A motivating “base” for attaching the things to be learned (Silander, 2015a, p. 18).

Phenomenon-based learning starts with observation of a phenomenon from different points of view. Silander (2015b) argues that phenomenon-based learning consists of five dimensions: holisticity, authenticity, contextuality, problem-based inquiry learning and learning process. Depending on how the specific approach is implemented in a classroom, the results can range from a superficial study of the phenomena with limited evidence to a more advanced application of learning. In its advanced potential, holisticity refers to the multidisciplinary of phenomenon-based learning, which is not integrated in traditional school subjects but rather focuses on a systematic, comprehensive exploration of current and actual events in the real world. Authenticity implies the use of methods, tools and materials, which are necessary in real-world situations to solve problems that are relevant to students’ lives and significant in the community. Theories and information have an immediate utility value, while experts and professionals from various fields are included in the learning community and learners are encouraged to take part in real expert culture and practices. A real environment, rather than a traditional classroom, is considered the authentic learning environment.

The third dimension, contextuality, refers to learning of phenomena as systemic entities, which are meaningful in a natural context and setting. In this sense, a phenomenon cannot be predefined but stays rather vague and ambiguous, as it is brought up by the students who observe their wider context. Through problem-based inquiry learning, students pose their own questions and collaboratively construct knowledge during the learning process, which is considered an intentional process of developing hypotheses and working theories. Learning tasks facilitate learning and guide students to become mindful of their learning (know-how). In its advanced stage, the students themselves plan the learning process by creating their own learning tasks and tools. Scaffolding is necessary for students to move beyond what they currently know toward what is to be known (Silander, 2015 b).

At the same time, phenomenon-based teaching is embedded in a problem-solving environment, where the teacher starts by posing questions or problems and the students “build

answers together to questions or problems posed concerning a phenomenon that interests them” (Silander, 2015 a, p. 17). Instructional goals are negotiated, not imposed, and evaluation serves as a self-analysis tool. Teaching is learner-centred, and theories to be learned by the students are connected to practical situations and phenomena. To address the study of phenomena in its holisticity, team teaching with different subject teachers is considered an important way of working (Silander, 2015b). In the learning process, teachers are seen as facilitators of learning tasks, who use their expertise not necessarily to transmit facts but, more important, to encourage and guide students to deal with a problem students themselves have identified (Silander, 2015 b).

These tools enable students to engage in hands-on experiences, encouraging them to articulate their thoughts, ideas, and opinions effectively. By actively participating in discussions and projects, students develop confidence and fluency in speaking. Last but not least learning with real cases like phenomenon –based learning engages students to the study and rises their interest double.

3 .Critical implications from a phonological perspective

Halinen (2014) maintained that the content of teaching, pedagogy and school practices should be renewed in relation to the changing environment within which schools operate and the skills needed to build a sustainable future. One way to achieve this renewal is to introduce multidisciplinary learning modules and phenomena in the new Finnish core curriculum. The new national curriculum addresses learning as a goal-oriented and lifelong process, in which students reflect on their learning, experiences and emotions and assume responsibility for the learning process (FNBE,2016). Students, who are considered to be “active actors” in their lifelong learning cycles, are to become mindful of their own learning and acquire strategies of *how* to learn, a joyful, creative and reflective activity to ensure a good life (FNBE, 2016,section 2.3). Competence, the buzzword of the 21st century, lies at the heart of this conceptualization of learning, which is essentially constructivist and psychological.

While all these characteristics sound fair and nobody will veto the importance of the seven transversal competence areas, a pedagogically and phenomenologically oriented learning perspective adds ingredients to this conceptualization that avoid students’ getting all the blame if learning endeavors fail. It seems to be the sole responsibility of the students to accumulate knowledge, solve problems, learn independently and collaboratively, become culturally multiliterate, become confident in expressing themselves and reflective about their own learning.

To some extent, phenomenon-based learning stems from reform pedagogical approaches to teaching and learning that are characterized by emotive words such as holisticity, child-centeredness and lifeworld, and appear to neglect the complexity of educational situations. Phenomenological conceptions of learning emphasize making experiences [*Erfahrungen machen*], which is different from constructing knowledge. It gives credit to an element of uncertainty and the belief that neither teaching, nor learning can be fully instructed, and that the former does not necessarily result in the latter. Pedagogically and phenomenologically oriented approaches to teaching and learning regard both sides of the same coin as essentially social activities that reflect contemporary as well as historical dimensions of sociality. One should beware of educational reform and policy making that tends to shift the responsibility for learning outcomes onto the students and reduces the teaching job to facilitating, mediating and organizing multidisciplinary learning modules. Pedagogically and phenomenologically oriented approaches to learning and teaching conceptualize this relation as a responsive one. (Agostini, 2015; Meyer-

Drawe, 1987; Waldenfels, 2009; Westphal, 2015). Neither teachers nor students alone contribute to successful learning outcomes, but within their responsive relation occurs a transformation that is the work of both.

4. Conclusion

Phenomenon-based learning technology holds significant potential for developing high school students' skills. By providing engaging and interactive learning experiences, fostering critical thinking and problem-solving skills, promoting collaborative learning and communication, and facilitating authentic assessment, PBL technology equips students with the necessary tools to become effective speakers. Educators should embrace this technology and incorporate it into their teaching practices to empower students and prepare them for success in their academic and professional lives. We can only experience articulations of phenomena through our senses. Thus, it is essential to recognize and embrace the complexity of this process, which is not an easygoing activity. As humans we live *in* the world and do not construct it. This complexity also applies to learning situations at school that cannot be fully instructed, even though this does not make careful planning and preparation obsolete. In a phenomenological perspective it, rather, calls for embracing the fact that gaining a new perspective requires letting go of an old one – a painful process. Educators must be prepared to guide students carefully in this process.

From a phenomenological perspective, learning as an experience implies that students must undergo experiences; they cannot construct them. And this situation gives rise to an element of uncertainty and ambivalence, which educators need to be prepared to encounter.

Last but not least, phenomenology argues for the responsive relation between teaching and learning, which in itself is a third dimension that comes into being through the common endeavors of teachers and students. This unity, overlooked by approaches that focus predominantly on teaching or predominantly on learning, is essential when the purpose is educational. It is therefore our task as educators to reclaim learning for pedagogy.

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